

Polarographic and Infrared Studies on the Complexes of Cobalt Ammines with Schiff's Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Vanillin and Amino Acids

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The interaction of chloropentaammine or *cis*-chloroaquo tetraammine cobalt (III) chloride with Schiff's bases (derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with glycine (S-Gly), Aspartic acid (S-A) and Glutamic acid (S-G), and *o*-vanillin with glycine (V-Gly), Aspartic acid (V-A) and Glutamic acid (V-G)) has been studied polarographically in aqueous medium and the composition of these more stable and brown coloured complexes has been established by chemical analysis, equivalent conductance, infrared spectra and polarographic data. The polarographic reduction of these complexes is found to be diffusion controlled but irreversible in nature.

EXTENSIVE studies¹⁻⁵ have been carried out on the metal complexes of Schiff's base derived from salicylaldehyde, vanillin and amino acids. These complexes provide valuable information, since they form intermediates in biological transamination^{6,7} reactions and form simple models for the complicated metal-pyridoxal-amino acid systems. However, little attention has been paid to the substitution reactions in metal complexes involving Schiff's bases. Studies have, therefore, been carried out polarographically on the direct substitution of some Schiff's bases, derived from amino acids, in cobalt(III)-amine complexes.

Materials and Methods

The Schiff's bases were prepared by the method of Dietrich *et al.*⁸ from salicylaldehyde or vanillin and amino acids. Salicylaldehyde was purified by distillation prior to use. Glycine, Aspartic acid, Glutamic acid and vanillin were A.R. grade (BDH) reagents. *cis*-chloropentaamminecobalt(III) chloride and *cis*-chloroaquo tetraamminecobalt(III) chloride were prepared^{9,10} from cobalt chloride.

The Schiff's base substituted cobalt(III) penta and tetraammines were prepared by the following method:

0.01 mole of the Schiff's base was added to 200 ml of a solution containing (0.01 mole) of chloropentaammine or *cis*-chloroaquo tetraamminecobalt(III) chloride. The mixture was gradually heated to 60° and maintained at this temperature for about 1 hr. when it turned brown. This solution was concentrated to about 50 ml under reduced pressure (below 40 mm of Hg) at 60°. It was then cooled to about 10° and a few drops of ice cold hydrochloric acid

added. The solution was shaken vigorously and allowed to stand for about 1/2 hr in an ice bath when brown crystals of the Schiff's base substituted complex were obtained. These were filtered off, washed with alcohol and recrystallised from a minimum quantity of water using ice-cold hydrochloric acid and alcohol. The recrystallised product was washed with alcohol, then acetone and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. The complexes were prepared using Schiff's bases derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with glycine (S-Gly), Aspartic acid (S-A) and Glutamic acid (S-G) and *o*-vanillin with glycine (V-Gly), Aspartic acid (V-A) and Glutamic acid (V-G) respectively.

Polarograms were recorded with a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a d.m.e. of $m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 3.75 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$. The solutions were held at 60° for 1 hr and allowed to equilibrate at 30° for 1/2 hr. The requisite amount of supporting electrolyte was then added and the solutions deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for about 10 min before recording the polarograms. All measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The equivalent conductance values of the complexes were determined using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (type CL01/01A).

The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr discs using a Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer. The complexes were decomposed by boiling with hydrochloric acid and cobalt estimated gravimetrically^{11,12}. Chloride ions outside the coordination sphere were estimated¹² by precipitating with AgNO_3 as AgCl . Results of carbon and nitrogen estimation were obtained from CDR, Lucknow.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of chloropentaamminecobalt(III) chloride(A) with different Schiff's bases studied

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resulted in the substitution of the coordinated chloride ion to give the Schiff's base substituted pentaamminecobalt(III) complex. In these cases the Schiff's base functions as a monodentate ligand.

Similarly, interaction of cischloroquo tetraamminecobalt(III) chloride (B) with the above mentioned Schiff's bases, resulted in the substitution of coordinated chloride and water to give the Schiff's base substituted tetraamminecobalt(III) complex. Here the Schiff's bases act as bidentate ligands.

The resulting brown coloured, soluble complexes were studied polarographically. The limiting current for each system was found to be diffusion controlled as evidenced by linear plots of i_d vs. $h_{eff}^{1/2}$. Plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ show that the waves are irreversible. The $E_{1/2}$ of the cobalt(III)-ammine complexes show shift towards more negative potentials in increasing concentration of the Schiff's bases. Since the waves are irreversible, the classical method of Lingane¹³ could not be used for studying the complex ion formation. Therefore, the method recommended by Tamamushi and Tanaka¹⁴ was employed. According to them :

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta \log C_x} = -j \frac{0.06014}{n\alpha} \quad \dots (1)$$

where α is the fraction of the total applied potential that favours the forward reaction and ' j ' is the number of ligands bound to the metal. The value of $n\alpha$ is given by the equation :

$$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = \frac{-0.0574}{n\alpha} \quad \dots (2)$$

The value of $\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta \log C_x$ is determined from the slope of the plots of $\log C_x$ vs $E_{1/2}$ where C_x is the concentration of the Schiff's base. The value of j thus obtained works out to be approximately 1.0 in all the cases showing thereby that one mole of Schiff's base combines with 1 mole of the metal ion. It may therefore be concluded that 1 : 1 interaction takes place between A or B and the Schiff's bases. The stability constants of the Schiff's base complexes were also calculated from the polarographic data and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE SCHIFF'S BASE COMPLEXES

Complex of		Stability constant log K
<i>Pentaammine cobalt(III) with</i>		
1. S-Gly	1.2	0.63
2. S-A	1.1	2.68
3. S-G	1.3	1.63
4. V-Gly	1.1	3.38
5. V-A	1.0	2.67
6. V-G	1.3	1.69
<i>Tetraammine cobalt(III) with</i>		
7. S-Gly	1.0	4.61
8. S-A	1.2	3.58
9. S-G	1.1	3.05
10. V-Gly	1.1	3.65
11. V-A	1.2	3.67
12. V-G	1.0	2.53

Chemical analysis of these complexes shows that one mole each of A or B and the Schiff's base react to give the substitution product. The equivalent conductance values are in accord with formation of monovalent complex-ions (except with (V-Gly) which gives a divalent moiety) in the case of tetraammines and bivalent complex-ions in the case of pentaammines.

The important infrared spectral characteristics of these complexes are given in Table 2. The infrared

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SCHIFF'S BASE COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Complex	$\nu(\text{NH}_3)$	Asym.		$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$
		$\nu(\text{CO}\bar{\text{O}})$	$\nu(\text{CO}\bar{\text{O}})$	
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{S-Gly})]\text{Cl}_2$	3140	1620	1430	1640
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{S-A})]\text{Cl}_2$	3160	1600	1400	1620
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{S-G})]\text{Cl}_2$	3300 3160	1600	1400	1620
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{V-Gly})]\text{Cl}_2$	3160	1600	1400	1630
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{V-A})]\text{Cl}_2$	3160	1600	1400	1640
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{V-G})]\text{Cl}_2$	3400	1600	1400	1630
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{S-Gly})]\text{Cl}_2$	3360 3160	1600	1400	1620
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{S-A})]\text{Cl}$	3400 3130	1600	1400	1630
9. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{S-G})]\text{Cl}$	3300 3120	1600	1380	1640
10. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{V-Gly})]\text{Cl}_2$	3300 3200	1600	1400	1620
11. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{V-A})]\text{Cl}$	3280 3120	1620	1390	1630
12. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{V-G})]\text{Cl}$	3400 3120	1600	1400	1640

spectra of Schiff's base substituted chloropentaammine cobalt(III) chloride shows binding of the Schiff's base through the carboxylic group. This conclusion is drawn from the fact that more pronounced bands around 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ appear, which may be assigned to the symmetric stretching of the coordinated carboxylic group and overlap of the asymmetric stretching of the carboxylic group and ammonia deformation mode respectively. The presence of these two bands coupled with the absence of the absorption around 1700 cm⁻¹ (due to normal carbonyl absorption of the -COOH group of the Schiff's base) provides evidence to confirm the coordination of the Schiff's base to cobalt through the carboxylic group¹⁵.

The infrared spectra of the tetraammines shows binding of the Schiff's base through the carboxylic groups in the case of (S-A), (S-G), (V-A) and (V-G) while in the case of (S-Gly) and (V-Gly), the binding is through the carboxylic group and the nitrogen of the C = N group. The infrared spectra shows bands

around 1600 and 1400 cm^{-1} corresponding to symmetric stretching of the coordinated carboxylic group and overlap of the asymmetric stretching of the carboxylic group and ammonia deformation mode respectively in all the complexes. In the cases of (S-A), (S-G), (V-A) and (V-G) and their tetraammine cobalt complexes, the C = N stretching frequency appears at the same frequency in the region 1640–1620 cm^{-1} . Since there is no shift in C = N frequency on coordination of the Schiff's base, it is evident that the nitrogen of this group is not involved in coordination in these complexes. In the case of (S-Gly) and (V-Gly), the C = N stretching frequency appears at 1640 cm^{-1} and 1630 cm^{-1} which shows shift to 1620 cm^{-1} in their tetraammine complexes, thereby showing binding through nitrogen of the C = N group¹⁸.

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